

UDC [027.7:005] (045)

DAVYDOVA I. O.

Department of Information, Library and Archives, Kharkiv State Academy of Culture (Kharkiv, Ukraine), e-mail IDavydova1@ukr.net, ORCID ID 0000-0001-6015-2477

EFFICIENCY OF MANAGING THE RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF UNIVERSITY LIBRARY

Objective. The paper investigates the resource potential of higher education institution libraries as a tool for effective management of their activity. **Methods.** The author pays attention to the difference between the concepts of "resource pool" and "resource potential", which is in involving the latter in the process of library information production and service. **Results.** The composition of the university library's resource potential is determined. It is stated that the effective management of the resource potential requires the managers to fully evaluate the factors of the internal and external environment of the library functioning. Characterization of individual components of the university library resource potential is given, and the need for their integrated use is emphasized. Much attention is paid to library staff as a leading resource of the management system, the formation of their cognitive potential. **Conclusions.** It is stated that the efficiency of the activity of the modern library of the higher education institution is largely determined by the available resource potential aimed at the achievement of scientifically and educationally significant goals and objectives of strategic character. The main results of the research can be used in the process of managing the activities of the university library.

Keywords: library; higher education institution; resource potential; management

Introduction

Sustainable development of the library of higher education institutions in the conditions of rapid and powerful technological, organizational, service transformations depends directly on effective management and requires finding ways to solve certain significant problems concerning the efficient use of their resource potential. In modern circumstances, we observe different models of adaptation of university libraries to the rapidly changing educational and information space: from traditionally functioning book depository with minimal level of service to active innovative strategies for implementing information and communication technologies, forming a qualitatively new resource base in the digital space, mastering mobile forms of information service.

Problem statement. Uneven pace of modernization of libraries of higher education institutions in Ukraine requires finding ways and mechanisms to overcome such a situation, the identification of factors that affect the effectiveness of library and information activities in the electronic information space of science and education. This involves directing efforts to master the modern methods of managing the university library's resource potential in accordance with changes in the concept of libraries' tasks, their role and place in the infrastructure of a higher education institution.

Methods

The resource potential of a university library is a multifaceted concept and is broadly defined as the set of resources and capabilities that an institution can use to achieve certain goals (Svirgun, & Sokolovska, 2012). In the scientific works of representatives of library-specific knowledge, this problem was investigated only at the level of its individual components: management of technical and technological, personnel, material, information, financial and management resources.

The vast majority of research is devoted to the analysis of technical and technological resources as the main tool for presenting a scientific library in the electronic environment. Thus, K. Lobuzina (2012) made a systematic analysis of the problems of adaptation, implementation and administration of modern automated library-information systems, analyzed the issues of management of technical and technological resources in the processes of creating electronic catalogues, full-text databases, activities on complex automation of library processes. The high technological level of modern university library is a factor of its successful modernization. This opinion is substantiated in the scientific researches of T. Kolesnykova (2015, 2019), I. Lobuzin (2017), O. Marina (2017) and D. Solovianenko (2007). Analyzing the role and place of the library in the modern system of social communications, O. Marina (2017) notes that "for most libraries in different countries of the world, nowadays technology is connected with approbation of new communication realities of digital space".

Scientific intelligence on managing the library's technological potential is complemented by works that analyze human resources. Researchers emphasize the importance of improving qualitatively the management of library staff, which directly ensure the appropriate level of technological processes, quality of information products and services. First of all, it involves the quality of library and information education as an important component of the quality of personnel resources of the libraries of higher education institutions (Solianik, 2013). Of particular importance for understanding the problem of resource potential of the university library is the study of issues of managing their activities. These aspects of the problem in the professional scientific environment are considered both within the framework of the innovative development of libraries and the formation of their innovation policy (Davydova, 2014), modern management technologies (Nikolaienko, 2014, 2015), and within the implementation of a balanced scorecard as the basis of strategic library management (Brui, 2015).

Thus, an analysis of the results of research on the resource components of the university library shows that the conceptualization of this important issue, both in theoretical and in practical terms, has not reached the required level of generalization in library science yet.

Purpose of the article. The main purpose of the research is to identify the components of the resource potential of the university library, to outline modern approaches to managing its effective use.

Results and Discussion

The resource potential of the library of a higher education institution is characterized by its cumulative ability in solving certain tasks that arise in the course of functioning of the university book depository. It integrates the resources of the institution that significantly affect the priority activities of both the university as a whole and its most important infrastructure component – the library. Today, the library should take a leading role in the development of the university's digital infrastructure by supporting science and the educational process. The main focus is on the creation of modern electronic search systems, full-text databases, the provision of innovative library services, including information support for scientific activities, scientometric research, the creation of publicly available archives of scientific information and user service through mobile devices.

Effective management of a library's resource potential must be based on a systematic approach and begin with the identification of its components. In the study, we propose to consider the resource potential of a library not only as a set of resources at its disposal, but also as the ability of employees and managers of all levels of management to use the resources to produce information products and services. Thus, the resource potential of the library characterizes not all the diversity of specific resources, but only that part of it, which is involved

in the process of library-information production and service, taking into account available information needs, scientific, educational and economic expediency, technological advances of scientific and technological progress. What is important is that effective resource management is focused not only on the library's existing system of resources, but also covers new (possibly alternative) resources and their sources that set the boundaries of current and future development.

The components of the university library resource potential are both material and immaterial resources:

- Employees and managers at all levels of management (demographic indices - age, gender; employee qualifications - education; cognitive capabilities - the desire for change; the ability to adapt to new requirements; cognitive abilities; cognitive development);
- Material and technical resources (library buildings, furniture, computers, telecommunication equipment, development opportunities);
- Technological resources (technologies of traditional and modern digital library-information production);
- Financial (availability and adequacy of financing; the amount of own and borrowed financial resources available to the library to meet current and future expenses);
- Information (arrays and flows of documents on printed media; own-produced and borrowed databases; digital content; management information; effective system of external and internal communications).

Specialists also consider a set of resources that are necessary for the implementation of the management process in the institution - resources of the management system, the components of which may be: resources of the organizational structure of the management system, management personnel, information resources, management techniques, management technologies (Fedulova, 2007). Each of these types of resources represents a set of opportunities to achieve the goals of the institution.

Effective management of the resource potential of a higher education institution's library requires management's ability to assess both internal factors affecting the status of the resource potential and external ones, as well as to apply appropriate countermeasures when needed. For example, global technological changes, the development of networked information space, the evolution of high-tech communication tools have contributed to the increased impact of technological resources on all spheres of library activity and led to changes in the technical paradigms of library information production. The rapid emergence of new hardware, software, telecommunications and communications channels has accelerated the obsolescence of existing technological processes. In these conditions, the libraries of higher education institutions quickly assessed the potential of technological changes and intensified their work in the field of technological innovations, and mastered the possibilities of reengineering.

Reengineering of library-information processes is a set of technical-technological, innovative methods and means intended for cardinal improvement of the basic library performance indices through modeling, analysis and redesign of existing library-information processes. From an economic point of view, reengineering is understood as a fundamental reframing and radical redesign of an enterprise and its essential processes in order to achieve a significant improvement in the quality of operation.

The reengineering of library-information processes is aimed at separating and substantially improving of those key areas of activity that can provide a particular information institution with competitive advantages. It can be a rational organization of the technological process, which allows to minimize the costs of creating high quality products, the introduction of personnel management that effectively directs people's activities in the right direction, thus achieving the goals of the institution, the marketing policy, which increases the competitiveness of the product.

At the same time, adequate restructuring of other parts of the management system must be ensured, which is the essence of the reengineering concept. Such an approach, when applied, allows stabilizing the resource potential of the university library as an open system in a state of dynamic equilibrium with the external environment.

It is important to note that increasing the competitive capacity of the library, its dynamic and holistic development are ensured not by one of its elements, but by the close interaction of all components of the resource potential. Efficiency of management of this system is conditioned by the available management technologies and the extensive system of communications. The quality of information interaction between the subject and the object of management significantly influences the making of the optimal management decision, which is possible due to the comprehensive analysis of processes and problems of production, economic, marketing, financial and other activities with a focus on interests, strategic goals of the institution. The quality of management as a resource potential of the university library is influenced by the style of management, the degree of knowledge of causes and consequences, a clear understanding of the relations within the scope of information available.

Nowadays, in the conditions of diversification of the information service, the cognitive-communication mission of the university library is strengthened, its cognitive capacity is growing, which envisages the following activities: stimulating knowledge growth; selection and accumulation of information from external sources; preservation, classification, transformation, accessibility, dissemination and sharing of knowledge; its use in decision-making processes; translating knowledge into the production of information products, services, databases; assessment and protection of knowledge. Accordingly, the formation of the library cognitive potential is based on two interconnected components of the knowledge reproduction cycle: knowledge replication (simple knowledge reproduction), which involves the transfer and assimilation of already generated knowledge; and the production of knowledge (advanced knowledge reproduction) in which new knowledge is acquired.

With regard to university libraries, it should be noted that prior to the active development of information processes their documentary and information activities involved mainly knowledge replication. But in today's globalized environment, competitive advantage is first and foremost ensured by their production. Information professionals in the age of the Internet and multimedia technologies are becoming "knowledge workers" who create new material and intellectual products and an important place in these processes belongs to library workers. The need to solve cognitive problems poses certain requirements to the individual-communication features and professional qualities of librarians, in particular to the level of their professional potential. It should be emphasized that among the requirements for the professional qualities of library specialists, their level of communication competence has a special place due to the fact that the profession of librarian belongs to socio-economic types of work, where communication, which accompanies work activity and is an integral part of the library-information service, becomes a professionally significant component.

Conclusions

Thus, it can be stated that the efficiency of the activity of the modern library of a higher education institution is largely determined by the available resource potential aimed at achieving scientific and educational goals and objectives of strategic character. The main areas of further research should include the analysis of innovative technologies of the university library resource potential management, the development of measures for the organization and control of tasks to determine the strategy for the development of university library resource potential.

REFERENCES

- Bruï, O. (2015). Zbalansovana systema pokaznykiv yak osnova systemy stratehichnoho upravlinnia u bibliotekakh: teoretychni aspekty. *Visnyk Knyzhkovoï palaty*, 10, 26-30. Retrieved from http://eprints.rclis.org/28673/1/brui_BSC1.pdf (in Ukrainian)
- Davydova, I. O. (2014). Upravlinnia systemnymy transformatsiiamy bibliotek: do pytannia naukovoï orhanizatsii upravlinnia. *Visnyk Kharkivskoi derzhavnoi akademii kultury*, 45, 78-84. Retrieved from [file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/hak_2014_45_11%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/hak_2014_45_11%20(1).pdf) (in Ukrainian)
- Fedulova, L. (2007). Tekhnolohichna konkurentospromozhnist ekonomiky: vyklyky ta shliakhy dlia Ukrainy. *Ekonomist*, 12, 30-33. (in Ukrainian)
- Kliushnyk, I. A., Kolesnykova, T. O. & Shapoval, O. C. (2019) Unified Digital Infrastructure of the Modern Scientific Library on the Basis of Web Technologies. *Science and Transport Progress*, 1(79), 64-80. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15802/stp2019/160434>
- Kolesnykova, T., & Kliushnyk, I. (2015). Izdaniye nauchnoy pyeriodiki v univyersyietakh: novyye zadachi, uchastniki, tyekhnologii. *Science and Transport Progress*, 6(60), 183-197. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15802/stp2015/57105> (in Russian)
- Lobuzin, I. (2017). Tsifrovoy proekt nauchnoy biblioteki: tekhnologicheskie resheniya i organizatsiya dostupa k informatsii. *Biblioteki natsionalnykh akademiy nauk: problemy funktsionirovaniya, tendentsii razvitiya*, 14, 119-129. Retrieved from [file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/bnan_2017_14_15%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/bnan_2017_14_15%20(1).pdf) (in Russian)
- Lobuzina, K. (2012). *Tekhnolohii orhanizatsii znannievyykh resursiv u bibliotechno-informatsiinii diialnosti*. Kyiv: Natsionalna biblioteka Ukrainy imeni V. I. Vernadskoho. Retrieved from http://www.nbuv.gov.ua/sites/default/files/all_files/201410_artilces_field_dopmat_files/eif00000043.pdf (in Ukrainian)
- Marina, O. (2017). *Biblioteka v tsyfrovomu prostori*. Kharkiv: ChDAK. (in Ukrainian)
- Nikolaienko, N. N. (2014). Upravlencheskiy personal kak faktor povysheniya effektivnosti innovatsionnoy deyatel'nosti bibliotek. *Nauchnye i tekhnicheskije biblioteki*, 11, 29-38. Retrieved from http://www.gpntb.ru/ntb/ntb/2014/11/ntb_11_2_2014.pdf (in Russian)
- Nikolaienko, N. M. (2015) Dyversyfikatsiia tekhnolohii upravlinnia bibliotekoiu yak sotsiokomunikatsiinoiu ustanovoïu suspilstva. *Derzhava ta rehiony. Serii: Sotsialni komunikatsii*, 3, 21-27. Retrieved from [file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/drsk_2015_3_6%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/drsk_2015_3_6%20(1).pdf) (in Ukrainian)
- Svirgun, O., & Sokolovska, V. (2012). *Resursnyi potentsial pidpriemstva: teoretychni aspekty*. Retrieved from http://www.rusnauka.com/17_AND_2010/Economics/69284.doc.htm (in Ukrainian)
- Solovianenko, D. (2007). Biblioteka-2.0: kontseptsiiia biblioteki druhoho pokolinnia. *Bibliotechnyi visnyk*, 5, 10-20. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/bv_2007_5_2.pdf (in Ukrainian)
- Solianik, A. (2013). Kulturotsentricheskaya model modernizatsii vysshogo bibliotechno-informatsionnogo obrazovaniya. *Visnyk Kharkivskoi derzhavnoi akademii kultury*, 40, 31-41. Retrieved from file:///C:/Users/User/Desktop/Downloads/hak_2013_40_9.pdf (in Russian)

ДАВИДОВА І. О.

Каф. «Інформаційна, бібліотечна та архівна справа», Харківська державна академія культури (Харків, Україна), e-mail IDavydova1@ukr.net, ORCID ID 0000–0001–6015–2477

ЕФЕКТИВНІСТЬ УПРАВЛІННЯ РЕСУРСНИМ ПОТЕНЦІАЛОМ БІБЛІОТЕКИ УНІВЕРСИТЕТУ

Мета. У статті поставлено за мету дослідити ресурсний потенціал бібліотек закладів вищої освіти як інструмент ефективного управління їх діяльністю. **Методика.** Автор звертає увагу на різницю між поняттями "ресурсний пул" та "ресурсний потенціал", що полягає в залученні останнього до процесу виробництва та обслуговування бібліотечної інформації. **Результати.** Визначено склад ресурсного потенціалу університетської бібліотеки. Зазначено, що ефективне управління ресурсним потенціалом вимагає від керівників усебічної оцінки факторів внутрішнього та зовнішнього середовища функціонування бібліотеки. Надано характеристику окремих компонентів ресурсного потенціалу університетської бібліотеки та наголошено на необхідності їх комплексного використання. Велику увагу приділено бібліотечним працівникам як провідному ресурсу системи управління, формуванню їх пізнавального потенціалу. **Висновки.** Зазначено, що ефективність діяльності сучасної бібліотеки закладу вищої освіти спрямованої на досягнення науково-освітніх значущих цілей та завдань стратегічного характеру, багато в чому визначається наявним ресурсним потенціалом. Основні результати дослідження можуть бути використані в процесі управління діяльністю університетської бібліотеки.

Ключові слова: бібліотека; заклад вищої освіти; ресурсний потенціал; управління